

IPBES VA Chapter 6 - Review of gaps within the chapters of the IPBES Values Assessment

Code: IPBES_VA_6.4

Versioning: 02 (30.03.2022)

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5899737

Project leader(s)

Barbara Nakangu (barbara.nakangu@gmail.com)

Luciana Porter-Bolland (lucianaporter@gmail.com)

Researcher(s)

David Gonzalez (ipbestsuvalues@iies.unam.mx)

Gabriela Arroyo (ipbestsuvalues@iies.unam.mx)

Data curator(s)

Gabriela Arroyo (ipbestsuvalues@iies.unam.mx)

Description:

This review corresponds to the IPBES Values assessment Chapter 6. The methodology explained in this report highlights the research followed to identify the needs within the topics covered in the assessment, and to help provide an analysis and directions for the uptake of diverse values within decision-making processes aiming at transformative change.

Process overview:

Protocol:

Type of analysis/search/review: All the gaps (knowledge and operationalization) found by the chapters of the assessment were sent and compiled.

Search languages: English

Exact Search Date: January-April 2021

Sample extracted (A): 135 (A)

- **Fields extracted (A):**

- ID
- Chapter
- Relevant sub-section
- Knowledge Gaps (Research, Data)
- Operationalization/practice gaps (information, resource, capacity)
- General description of the gap identified and how it was identified (comment on the relevance of the gap)
- Comment on the relevance of the gap

Location and Format of the Data (A): IPBES_VA_6.4_04-29-2021_(A).csv

Treatment applied: Database was reviewed by cleaning up duplicates or summarising related gaps.

Type of analysis/search/review: Review of the Values Assessment chapters

Search languages: English

Exact Search Date: April-May 2021

Sample extracted (B): 108 (B)

- **Fields extracted (B):**
 - ID
 - Chapter
 - SOD section
 - Type of gap
 - Gap identified
 - Gap summarised

Location and Format of the Data (B): IPBES_VA_6.4_April-May2021_(B).csv

Treatment applied: For the analysis the decision cycle stages were used (further developed in section 6.5): clarify the purpose, recognise diverse values, understand the context, weigh up the trade offs, trace the decision chain, select policy options, find entry points and, reflect outcomes. Each gap was assessed against the decision cycle stage(s) they could be related to.

Sample extracted (C): 108 (C)

- **Fields extracted (C):**
 - ID
 - Chapter
 - SOD section
 - Type of gap
 - Gap
 - Short gap
 - Clarify the purpose
 - Recognise diverse values
 - Understand the context
 - Weigh up the trade-offs
 - Trace the decision chain
 - Select policy options
 - Find entry points
 - Reflect outcomes

Location and Format of the Data (C): IPBES_VA_6.4_June2021_(C).csv

Treatment applied: Gaps grouped in clusters in accordance to the topic addressed by each of them (D). The analysis kept the decision cycle stages related to the gaps clusters, while adding a capacity dimensions (motivational, analytical, bridging, negotiation, social network and governance) analysis (R1). There was an identification of the capacity or capacities that could be useful for addressing each of the gaps clusters (operationalization and knowledge). There

is also a column that explains the actions related to the identified capacities and that relate the best to each gap.

Type of analysis/search/review: Capacity dimensions gaps clusters analysis

Search languages: English

Exact Search Date: June 2021

Sample extracted (D): 39 (D)

● **Fields extracted (D):**

- Cluster
- Type of gap
- Description of gap cluster
- Short gap
- Gap IDs
- Related chapter sections
- Decision cycle (clarify the purpose, recognise diverse values, understand the context, weigh up the trade offs, trace the decision chain, select policy options, find entry points and, reflect outcomes)
- Capacity dimensions (motivational, analytical, bridging, negotiation, social network and governance)
- Actions related to capacities

Location and Format of the Data (D): IPBES_VA_6.4_June2021_(D).csv

Treatment applied: For the last analysis, there were identified Big Topics (Gaps in the representation of various types of knowledge and values, or Visibilization of the (or Empirical) role of values in policy) and the focus of each of the clusters (capacities, IPLC, resources, futures, ILK, justice and power, methods, futures, policy instruments, transformation, uptake in policy and values). Once there was identified the focus of each of the clusters it was possible to describe the groups of gaps found along the assessment relating them to the capacity dimensions and also, to the decision cycle stages.

Type of analysis/search/review: Identification of Big topics and focus of the gaps clusters.

Search languages: English

Exact Search Date: June 2021

Sample extracted (E): 40 (E)

● **Fields extracted (E):**

- Big Topic
- Focus of the gap
- Type of gap
- Cluster
- Short gap

Location and Format of the Data (E): IPBES_VA_6.4_June2021_(E).csv

Definition of files

ID	Name	File Type	Description of the file
A	IPBES_VA_6.4_04-29-2021_(A).csv	csv	Contains the gaps found in all the chapters of the Values Assessment
B	IPBES_VA_6.4_April-May2021_(B).csv	csv	Cleaned-up gaps database.
C	IPBES_VA_6.4_June2021_(C).csv	csv	Decision cycle analysis of the gaps.
D	IPBES_VA_6.4_June2021_(D).csv	csv	Gaps clusters and capacity dimensions analysis.
E	IPBES_VA_6.4_June2021_(E).csv	csv	Contains the results from the final criteria applied to the gaps.
R1	IPBES_VA_6.4_June2021_(R1)	pdf	List of the capacity dimensions criteria applied to the gaps clusters.